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Dietary replacement of soybean with microalgae meal during grower and finisher phases: effects on growth performance, occurrence of foot pad dermatitis, breast meat quality traits, and plasma and cecum metabolome of broiler chickens

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Introduction

- Growth of world population is increasing protein demand (feed or food)
- **Soybean**: most important protein source in commercial poultry feeding
- Cultivation, processing and transportation of soybean are becoming concerning from a sustainability standpoint

World Population

Projected world population until 2100

Interest in identifying **alternative protein sources** that might replace soybean in poultry diets while maintaining animal performance and health

Introduction

Microalgae meals (MM): sustainable alternative to soybean?

- ✓ Low environmental impact
- ✓ Excellent nutritional profile (high CP content with balanced essential AA profile)
- ✓ Beneficial effects on animal health and product quality

✗ Very limited use in current commercial practices

- High cost (at the moment, at least...)
- Relatively scarce knowledge on product composition, digestibility and optimal dietary inclusion rate

MM administration at 5, 10 or 15% during the first 22 d significantly impaired broilers growth performance ([poster ID: 2209](#))

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Aim

To evaluate the effects of the **dietary replacement of soybean with dehydrated microalgae meal (*Arthrospira spp.* - *Spirulina*)** during grower and finisher phases on:

- productive performance**
- occurrence of foot pad dermatitis (FPD)**
- breast meat quality traits**
- plasma and cecum metabolomics profile**

of fast-growing broiler chickens

Materials and Methods

Experimental design

1,000 d-old
Ross 308 ♂
chicks

Each group composed by 8 replicates of 25 birds/each

Experimental diets:

- **CON**: commercial soybean-based diet
- **CON + 3% MM**: CON with 3% microalgae meal
- **CON + 6% MM**: CON with 6% microalgae meal

- All diets were formulated to meet current nutritional recommendations
- Mash form
- *Ad-libitum* consumption

Analyzed chemical composition of microalgae meal (*Spirulina*)

Composition (<i>as is</i>)	%
Dry Matter	94.0
Crude protein	70.2
Crude fiber	4.68
Ash	7.33
Total fat	11.6
Calcium	0.31
Phosphorous	1.13
Sodium	0.63
Chlorine	0.13
AME (kcal/kg)*	3,000

* Estimated value

AA profile (% of CP)	MM	Reference#	
		Spirulina	SBM
Lysine	4.52	5.10	6.05
Methionine	2.26	2.12	1.33
Cysteine	0.90	0.99	1.43
Met. + Cys.	3.18	3.11	2.75
Threonine	4.60	4.50	3.86
Arginine	7.11	6.06	7.30
Isoleucine	5.31	4.40	4.56
Leucine	8.22	8.09	7.60
Valine	5.85	5.68	4.74
Histidine	1.48	1.65	2.59
Serine	4.50	4.15	4.99
Glycine	4.74	5.21	4.22
Proline	3.43	3.96	5.04
Alanine	7.19	7.30	4.31
Phenylalanine	4.49	4.71	5.10
Glutamic acid	13.5	11.43	11.4
Aspartic acid	9.79	8.82	17.9

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Materials and Methods

Ingredients and chemical composition of experimental diets

%	Starter	Grower			Finisher		
	CON	CON	CON + 3% MM	CON + 6% MM	CON	CON + 3% MM	CON + 6% MM
Corn	42.4	44.9	48.3	51.7	41.8	45.2	48.6
Wheat	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	13.0	13.0	13.0
Full-fat soybean	10.0	15.0 -16%	15.0 -32%	15.0	15.0 -20%	15.0 -40%	15.0
Soybean meal	22.3	18.1	12.6	7.09	12.4	6.87	1.34
Vegetable oil	2.12	2.87	2.00	1.12	4.07	3.19	2.32
Microalgae meal	0.00	0.00	3.00	6.00	0.00	3.00	6.00
Others	13.2	9.13	9.11	9.09	13.7	13.7	13.7

AME (kcal/kg)	3.03	3.15	3.15	3.15	3.27	3.27	3.27
Crude protein	22.81	20.9	20.7	20.5	18.8	18.6	18.4
Lipid	5.97	7.66	7.22	6.78	8.90	8.46	8.02
Fiber	2.95	3.03	3.00	2.96	2.91	2.87	2.84
Ash	5.13	4.64	4.49	4.35	4.27	4.12	3.97
Lysine (total)	1.40	1.26	1.26	1.26	1.10	1.10	1.10
Met + Cys (total)	1.05	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.87	0.87	0.87
Threonine (total)	0.95	0.85	0.85	0.85	0.75	0.75	0.75

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Materials and Methods

Evaluation of productive performance

- **Body weight (BW)** on a pen basis at 0, 14, 28, 43 d
- **Feed intake (FI)** on a pen basis at each diet switch (14, 28, 43 d)
- **Mortality** (daily; number and weight)

**Daily Weight Gain (DWG), Daily Feed Intake (DFI)
and Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)**

41 d : Processing
(commercial slaughterhouse)

Birds and carcasses belonging to different dietary treatments were clearly identified and kept separated throughout the processing phases

- **Slaughter yields:**

- Carcass
- Breast
- Legs
- Wings

- Incidence and severity of **foot pad dermatitis (FPD):**

- on all birds (1 foot/bird)
- 3-point scale scoring system

Evaluation of breast meat quality traits

Technological traits (15 breasts/group)

- pHu (24 h postmortem)
- Lightness (L^*)
- Redness (a^*)
- Yellowness (b^*)
- Drip loss (%)
- Cooking loss (%)
- Shear force (kg)

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Materials and Methods

41 d

**Plasma and ceca
content samples**
(16 birds/group)

**Proton Nuclear
Magnetic Resonance
(¹H-NMR)
spectrometry**

Results

Productive performance (0-41 d)

Parameter	Experimental groups					SEM	P value	Contrasts					
	CON	F3	F6	GF3	GF6			Diet		MM dosage		MM duration	
								CON	MM	3%	6%	F	G + F
BW 41 d (g/bird)	2,541 A	2,454 AB	2,412 B	2,445 AB	2,384 B	15.6	<0.01	2,541 A	2,424 B	2,450	2,398	2,433	2,414
DWG (g/bird/d)*	59.6 a	58.7 ab	57.6 ab	57.5 ab	56.0 b	0.38	0.03	59.6 a	57.4 b	58.1	56.8	58.1	56.8
DFI (g/bird/d)*	106.2	106.1	105.5	108.4	108.1	0.50	n.s.	106.2	107.1	107.3	106.8	105.8 b	108.3 a
FCR*	1.785 B	1.810 B	1.834 AB	1.886 AB	1.934 A	0.02	<0.01	1.785 b	1.866 a	1.848	1.884	1.822 B	1.910 A
Mortality (%)	3.00	3.00	2.52	1.00	1.00	0.02	n.s.	3.00	1.88	2.00	1.76	2.76	1.00

* Corrected for mortality; A,B: P<0.01; a,b: P<0.05.

Results

Slaughter yields at 41 d

n.
CON = 151
F3 = 167
F6 = 166
GF3 = 166
GF6 = 165

Not statistically
evaluated

Results

Incidence and severity of FPD at 41 d

n.
CON = 152
F3 = 149
F6 = 170
GF3 = 164
GF6 = 168

X² P-value = n.s.

Results

Breast meat quality traits (n = 15 breasts/group) – color profile

Parameter	Experimental groups					SEM	P value	Contrasts							
	CON	F3	F6	GF3	GF6			Diet		MM dosage		MM duration			
								CON	MM	3%	6%	F	G + F		
Raw meat	Lightness (L*)	57.9 a	56.6 ab	54.5 bc	54.3 c	52.6 c	0.31	<0.001	57.9 A	54.5 B	55.5 A	53.5 B	55.6 A	53.4 B	↓
	Redness (a*)	1.67 b	1.65 b	2.69 a	2.72 a	3.13 a	0.10	<0.001	1.67 B	2.55 A	2.19 B	2.91 A	2.17 B	2.93 A	↑
	Yellowness (b*)	6.77 d	12.7 c	17.0 b	17.2 b	20.1 a	0.59	<0.001	6.77 B	16.7 A	15.0 B	18.5 A	14.9 B	18.6 A	↑
Cooked meat	Lightness (L*)	83.7 a	83.4 ab	82.4 bc	82.4 bc	81.8 c	0.17	<0.001	83.7 A	82.5 B	82.9 a	82.1 b	82.9 a	82.1 b	↓
	Redness (a*)	2.15 B	2.44 B	3.10 A	3.14 A	3.55 A	0.09	<0.001	2.15 B	3.06 A	2.80 B	3.32 A	2.77 B	3.35 A	↑
	Yellowness (b*)	13.6 D	17.5 C	20.7 B	20.3 B	23.5 A	0.43	<0.001	13.6 B	20.5 A	18.9 B	22.1 A	19.1 b	21.9 a	↑

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Results

Breast meat quality traits (n = 15 breasts/group) – color profile

Results

Breast meat quality traits (n = 15 breasts/group) – technological properties

Parameter	Experimental groups					SEM	P value	Contrasts					
	CON	F3	F6	GF3	GF6			Diet		MM dosage		MM duration	
								CON	MM	3%	6%	F	G + F
pHu	5.76	5.73	5.74	5.74	5.79	0.01	n.s.	5.76	5.75	5.74	5.77	5.74	5.77
Drip loss (%)	1.87 a	1.87 a	1.75 ab	1.61 ab	1.54 b	0.04	<0.05	1.87	1.69	1.74	1.65	1.81	1.57
Cooking loss (%)	23.4	22.7	22.5	24.0	22.8	0.23	n.s.	23.4	23.0	23.3	22.6	22.5	23.4
Shear force (kg)	2.1	2.2	2.1	2.1	1.9	0.04	n.s.	2.1	2.1	2.2	2.0	2.2	2.0

a,b: P<0.05.

Results

NMR metabolomics profile – plasma

Results

NMR metabolomics profile – ceca content

Microbiota
analysis

Coming
SOON

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Conclusions

- The administration of **6% microalgae meal** during grower or finisher phase **impaired growth performance** of broiler chickens, whereas a **3% inclusion was partially tolerated**
- **No significant effect** was observed on the incidence and severity of **foot pad dermatitis**
- Microalgae meal showed **excellent meat pigmentation capacity** regardless of the dosage, whereas other meat quality traits were only slightly affected by the dietary treatment
- **Plasma and cecum metabolome showed relevant variations** in response to MM administration that, along with other *-omics* insights, could provide important information on the effects of this nutritional strategy on bird metabolism

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PROTEINS

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Thanks for your attention!

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Microalgae production system

VAXA

impact nutrition

www.vaxa.life

Picture taken for VAXA website

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